

Stepwise Stability Constants of Trivalent Scandium, Yttrium, Lanthanum, Cerium, Praseodymium and Neodymium Complexes with Ammonium Aurintricarboxylate : A Potentiometric Study

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Manuscript received 26 December 1975 ; accepted 9 March 1976

Potentiometric studies on the free ligand and the metal complexes of Sc(III), Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) with ammonium aurintricarboxylate (Aluminon) were carried out in aqueous medium. The stepwise stability constants of these complexes formed were computed by Bjerrum-Calvin pH-titration technique, as used by Irving and Rossotti at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.02 M (NaClO₄). The trend in the stability constant values of the metal chelates has been found to be Y(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III).

THE review of the literature shows that extensive work has been carried out on the complexes of different metal ions with ammonium aurintricarboxylate, spectrophotometrically¹⁻⁵, but very little attention has been drawn towards potentiometric studies^{6,7}. However, no reference could be traced out in literature on the study of the stepwise stability constants of ammonium aurintricarboxylate complexes with rare earths. Thus in the present work, complexes of Sc(III), Y(III), La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III) and Nd(III) with ammonium aurintricarboxylate have been studied. The methods used are the same as described in previous communication⁸. The 'practical' proton-ligand stability constants and stepwise metal-ligand stability constants at 30° are obtained by the Bjerrum-Calvin titration technique^{10,11} as used by Irving and Rossotti.

Experimental

Materials and Methods: The solutions of metal ions were prepared by taking requisite quantities of metal oxides viz. Sc₂O₃, Y₂O₃, La₂O₃, Pr₂O₃, Nd₂O₃ and chlorides such as CeCl₃ and dissolving them in minimum quantities of perchloric acid. The excess acid was evaporated and solutions made after adding known quantity of perchloric acid, to prevent hydrolysis. These solutions were standardized by EDTA method⁹. The stock solution (0.02M) of ammonium aurintricarboxylate (BDH, England) was freshly prepared by dissolving requisite quantity of it, in double distilled water. Sodium hydroxide (1 M), perchloric acid (0.1 M), sodium perchlorate (0.2M) and potassium hydrogen phthalate (0.05 M) were prepared in the usual manner, in carbon dioxide free double distilled water.

A pH-meter with a combined glass-calomel electrode assembly, was employed to determine the change in hydrogen ion concentrations of the solutions during the titration. The cell in which the titrations were carried out was so designed that the titrations were always carried out in the atmosphere of nitrogen and the

contents of the cell were stirred continuously during the titration by electrically working glass stirrer. The temperature of the cell was maintained by immersing the cell in an electronically maintained thermostat having an accuracy of ±0.1°.

Bjerrum-Calvin Titrations Three mixtures were prepared as follows :

Mixture A : 1.0 × 10⁻² M perchloric acid
Mixture B : 1.0 × 10⁻² M perchloric acid + 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand
Mixture C : 1.0 × 10⁻² M perchloric acid + 5.0 × 10⁻³ M ligand
+ 1.0 × 10⁻³ M Metal.

Appropriate quantities of 0.2M sodium perchlorate was added to each of these mixtures so as to keep the ionic strength constant (0.02M NaClO₄). The final volume in all the mixtures was adjusted to 100 ml with double distilled water. The ratio of the metal and ligand was always 1:5.

Results and Discussion

"Practical" proton-ligand stability constants : In order to calculate the stepwise stability constants of the metal complexes, it becomes necessary to have a prior knowledge of the "Practical" proton-ligand stability constants. The values of \bar{n}_A at different pH-values were obtained from the acid and ligand titration curves. The equation (1) was used to determine the values of \bar{n}_A at a particular pH value.

$$\bar{n}_A = Y - \{ (V'' - V')(N^\circ + E^\circ) \} / (V^\circ + V')T_{CL}^\circ \quad \dots (1)$$

The values of \bar{n}_A so obtained were plotted against the corresponding pH-values (Fig. 1), and "Practical" proton-ligand stability constants were obtained by applying various "computational methods"^{1,2}, which are tabulated below in Table 1.

TABLE 1—"PRACTICAL" PROTON-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF AMMONIUM AURINTRICARBOXYLATE AT 30°, AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.02M NaClO₄

Method	Constants		
	log K ₁ ^H	log K ₂ ^H	log β ^H
A	8.970	8.080	17.050
B	9.040	7.968	17.008
C	9.061	8.139	17.200

Method A : refers to interpolation at half \bar{n} -values method.
 Method B : refers to interpolation at various \bar{n} -values method.
 Method C : refers to midpoint method.

Fig. 1 : Formation Curve for Proton-Ligand at 30°C, at an ionic strength of 0.02 M NaClO₄.

Curves in Fig. 1 were extended between 0 and 2 on \bar{n}_A scale which indicates dissociation of ammonium aurintricarboxylate (H₂AAC) in the following manner :

Stepwise metal-ligand stability constants : The stepwise stability constant of a metal chelate is given by the equation (2).

$$K_n = C_{MLn} / C_{MLn-1} \cdot C_L \quad (\text{Where } n=1,2, \dots, N) \dots (2)$$

Where K_n is called the nth metal-ligand stability constant.

The stepwise stability constants were obtained by plotting \bar{n} against p^L, where \bar{n} is the average number of ligands attached per metal ion and is given by the equation (3).

$$\bar{n} = (V'' - V')(N^0 + E^0) / (V^0 + V') \bar{n}_A T_{CM}^0 \dots (3)$$

where, T_{CM}⁰ denotes the total concentration of metal present in the solution and other terms have their usual meanings.

The free ligand exponent p^L has been calculated from equation (4).

$$p^L = \frac{\log \left\{ \sum_{n=0}^{n=j} \beta_n^H (1/\text{antilog } p^H)^n \cdot (V^0 + V'') \right\}}{\{(T_{CL}^0 - \bar{n} T_{CM}^0) \cdot V^0\}} \quad (4)$$

where β_n^H is the overall "Practical" proton-ligand stability constant.

Fig. 2. : Formation Curve for Metal-Ligand Y(III)-AAC at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.02 M NaClO₄.

The formation curves (Fig. 2) obtained by plotting \bar{n} against p^L shows that the values of \bar{n} in all the cases exceeded 2.5 thereby indicating that 1:1, 1:2 as well as 1:3 complexes are formed. Only in case of Sc(III), pK₁ could not be obtained because the value of \bar{n} at the point at which separation of ligand and metal curves started exceeded 0.5. The stepwise metal-ligand stability constants for the different metals at 30°, at an ionic strength of 0.02M. (NaClO₄) are tabulated below in Table 2.

TABLE 2—STEPWISE METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AT 30° AT AN IONIC STRENGTH OF 0.02M NaClO₄

Metal	Constants			
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₃	log β
Sc(III)	—	3.40	2.43	5.83
Y(III)	5.24	2.42	1.97	9.63
La(III)	3.30	1.84	1.64	6.78
Ce(III)	3.34	1.99	1.70	7.03
Pr(III)	3.40	2.14	1.80	7.34
Nd(III)	3.56	2.32	1.81	7.69

From Table 2 it is clear that all the metals under consideration, forms 1:1, 1:2 as well as 1:3 complexes with ammonium aurintricarboxylate. Only, in case of Sc(III), pK_1 could not be obtained. Also, it can be seen that both the protons from the two hydroxyl groups of ammonium aurintricarboxylate get dissociated while complexation. The trend of stability constants of the metal chelates is in order Y(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to the Director, Laxminarayan Institute of Technology for providing the necessary facilities for carrying out the work and also to the Director, National Environmental Engineering Research Institute, Nagpur for permitting one of them (S.D.M.) to work at L.I.T.

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